

Supplementary figures 1-3

Supplementary figure 1



Supplementary figure 1. Overview of the 12 largest scaffolds of the *P. retropinna* assembly. Statistics are displayed across bins(bars) and moving average(line).

Supplementary figure 2



Supplementary figure 2. Average nucleotide divergence across 500kb bins when aligning *P. retropinna* to *P. turrubarensis*, *P. retropinna* to *P. reticulata* and *P. turrubarensis* to *P. reticulata*. Bins are sorted from high to low divergence.

Supplementary figure 3



Supplementary figure 3. Raw PacBio sequencing reads mapped to the *P. retropinna* *vtg1* gene duplication.